

Steps to Unraveling the Mysteries of the World Order.

Article I. General Understanding of the Doppler Effect

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Abstract

This article proves that the Doppler effect is not a law of nature. And from this it follows that the relativistic theory is erroneous and unjustifiably accepted in physics. Also as a result of the study, a connecting factor was established that describes the real process during which the shift of the Fraunhofer dark lines in the spectra of electromagnetic waves occurs. A currently widespread misconception in understanding the Hubble law was discovered. Based on the results of the study, a completely new method for determining the possible motion of distant stars and galaxies and finding their radial velocities is proposed.

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Introduction

From early childhood, every person asks themselves questions, after they have begun to walk and see the world around. Finding the answers the person thereby learns the world. Thinking back to the time I was a preschooler, I used to peer into the distance, and seeing the edge of the horizon I would ask myself what is there on the edge of visibility. But as I walked into the distance, the horizon moved away, and I did not find the answer to the question posed. This is the way it is in science — the more we get to know the world around us, the wider the border of our unknown and unexplored becomes. Often,

putting the question of the structure of the whole world and its beginning, we do not find the agreement of our mind in the existing multifaceted family of theories on the world creation. In fact, all those interpretations of the Big Bang theory, of the multitude of mini-universes, of the existence of four and n-dimensional physical spaces do not have and do not give a common and unified initial knowledge of the laws of nature. After all, even ancient philosophers like Thales, Democritus, Socrates and his followers claimed that the world is one and everything in the world comes from one thing. These scientists laid the foundations and set out the rules for learning the truth as well as developed a scientific approach to the structure of principles for any science. Based on the postulates developed by them, the accepted theory of the world creation is supposed to explain everything — from the movement of bodies in the sky and on the Earth to the movement inside the atom. Unfortunately, the instructions of ancient philosophers are not fulfilled in modern physics; for example, the laws describing classical mechanics are not in harmony with the current quantum mechanics. That is, there is no single rule for describing motion in atoms and in larger bodies. In general, analyzing the currently existing theories of the creation of Everything, you only find that they do not give an understanding of the unity of the laws of nature. In their structure, they are very complex, cumbersome and incomprehensible, but nature does not like complexity, especially at the beginning of its creation.

For over 400 years of active development of physics and astronomy, human civilization has made a lot of discoveries of the laws of nature. Unfortunately, a large number of fundamental laws were adopted by scientists, pioneers of science, at a time when person did not have advanced technologies and had no experience in studying the atom or space. Relying on insufficiently complete information on the description of processes taking place in nature, it was difficult for them to mathematically correctly describe the studied law of nature. And if adopted incorrectly, even one physical law of nature leads to the piling of other false laws and theories. As a result, this leads the whole science to an illusory understanding of the structure of the whole Universe.

Finding a mistake in any matter is not as easy as it seems, especially in the matter of the worldview of the entire human civilization that has been established for several centuries. Sometimes, making a meaningful discovery in science is easier than finding errors in an already existing theory of physics. It is especially true if such contradictions are not one but several; then it is necessary to find agreement between the new theory and all sections of physics. We all know very well how difficult it was for N. Copernicus, T. Brahe, I. Kepler and G. Galilei to get their discoveries accepted by all layers of society. After all, the discoveries of these scientists not only affected individual sections of physics, but also changed the worldview of the whole society. At present, our science is also on the verge of adopting a new worldview, a new philosophy, a new physics. Studying the development of human thought and the experience accumulated over millennia of technology development, I have discovered the knowledge of explaining the processes taking place in nature. Having learnt a new philosophy of the World structure, at first I tried to connect it, in every possible way, with the recognized theories on the creation of the Universe and with the sections of physics accepted in everyday human life. However, the attempts to do

this have led me to the knowledge that radically changes the view of individual sections of physics. Developing my knowledge further and linking it to the existing physics, I have found errors in modern physics. I would like to point out that economically developed countries are currently investing a lot of money in the development of science. But, unfortunately, a lot of funded projects cannot yield a positive result, as scientists are looking for something that does not exist and can never be. Realizing how difficult it has been for scientists, at all times, to get their revolutionary works published, I still want to believe that my research work will be duly appreciated and published. After all, for any reviewer, scientist, editor-in-chief of a scientific publishing house, the truth has always been and will be most important. Without having true knowledge in science, there is no general knowledge, and Science cannot move forward.

1. The Doppler Effect

The Doppler principle was first announced on May 25, 1842 by Christian Doppler (1803–1853). The treatise “On the colored light of the binary stars” was heard by five people; the chairman was his mentor B. Bolzano, a philosopher and mathematician. Soon, the named treatise was published as a separate edition in the Proceedings of the Royal Society of Austrian scientists. In his article, Doppler considered light as propagating waves disturbed in the ether, because it was believed at that time that waves, like waves on water, could not move without filling space with a material medium. Doppler noted that the frequency of light oscillations ν , received by the observer depends both on the speed of light source v , and the speed of the observer, while the propagation medium (ether) is stationary.

For a more objective understanding of the issue under discussion, I will provide the proof of the Doppler principle set out in a modern physics textbook for students of higher technical educational establishments. When doing so, I will bring the designation of different values to the international understanding [1]. It is written verbatim in the textbook that *the Doppler effect is the change in the frequency of oscillations perceived by the receiver when the source of these oscillations and the receiver are in motion relative to each other. For example, it is known from experience that the tone of the train horn increases as it approaches the platform and decreases when it moves away, i.e. the movement of the oscillation source (horn) relative to the receiver (ear) changes the frequency of the received oscillations.*

To consider the Doppler effect, let us assume that the sound source and receiver are moving along a straight line connecting them.

Let us introduce the following designations:

- v_s – speed of sound source,*
- v_r – speed of sound receiver,*
- v – sound propagation velocity,*
- ν_0 – frequency of source oscillations,*
- ν – sound frequency registered by the receiver,*
- $T = 1/\nu$, where T – is the oscillation period.*

1.1 The source and the receiver are at rest relative to the medium,
i.e.

$$v_s = v_r = 0.$$

If v – is the sound propagation velocity in the medium under consideration, then the wavelength

$$\lambda = v T = \frac{v}{\nu_0}.$$

Propagating in the medium, the wave reaches the receiver and causes oscillations of the sound-sensitive element with a frequency of

$$\nu = \frac{v}{\lambda} = \frac{v}{vT} = \nu_0.$$

Therefore, sound frequency ν registered by the receiver is equal to frequency ν_0 at which the sound wave is emitted by the source.

1.2 The receiver is approaching the source while the source is at rest, i.e.

$$v_r > 0, v_s = 0.$$

In this case, the wave propagation velocity relative to the receiver equals $v + v_r$. Since the wavelength does not change here, then

$$\nu = \frac{v+v_r}{\lambda} = \frac{v+v_r}{vT} = \frac{(v+v_r)\nu_0}{v},$$

that is, the oscillation frequency perceived by the receiver is by $(v + v_r)/v$ times bigger than the oscillation frequency of the source.

1.3 The source is approaching the receiver while the receiver is at rest, i.e.

$$v_s > 0, v_r = 0.$$

The oscillation propagation speed depends only on the medium properties. Therefore, for the time equal to the source oscillation period, the wave emitted by the source will travel distance vT in the direction of the receiver (equal to wavelength λ), regardless of whether the source is moving or at rest. For the same time, the source will pass distance $v_s T$ in the direction of the wave (fig. 1), i.e. the wavelength in the direction of motion will decrease and equal as follows: $\lambda' = \lambda - v_s T = (v - v_s) T$, then

$$\nu = \frac{v}{\lambda'} = \frac{v}{(v-v_s)T} = \frac{v\nu_0}{v-v_s},$$

that is, the oscillation frequency ν perceived by the receiver will increase by $v/(v - v_s)$ times. In cases 2 and 3, if $v_s < 0$ and $v_r < 0$, the sign will be reverse.

1.4 The source and the receiver are moving relative to each other. Based on the results obtained for cases 2 and 3, it is possible to derive an expression for the oscillation frequency perceived by the receiver:

$$\nu = \frac{(v \pm v_r)}{v \mp v_s} \nu_0, \quad (1)$$

where the upper sign is taken if during the movement of the source or the receiver their convergence occurs; and the lower sign is taken if the source and the receiver are moving

away from each other.

It follows from the above formulas that the Doppler effect is different depending on whether the source and the receiver are in motion. If the direction of velocities v_r and v_s does not coincide with the straight line passing through the source and the receiver, it is necessary to take their projections for the straight line direction, instead of these velocities, for formula 1.

Figure 1. The Doppler effect in acoustics

The Doppler principle was not immediately accepted by scientists; there were objective reasons for that. Initially, it was decided to check Doppler's conclusions using sound waves. Several experiments were conducted that confirmed the change in sound waves perceived by the observer when the distance between the objects under study changed. In fact, it is difficult now to find a person who has not encountered changes in the sound of a working mechanism by ear, depending on the distance to it. Thus, indeed, if we are standing on the side of some not noisy road, we can hear a change in the sound of an approaching car, namely, a typical increase in the sound pitch, which indicates an increase in the oscillation frequency of sound waves. As the car moves away from us, we will hear a change in the sound characteristics in reverse order; that is, the sound pitch will decrease. We will feel the same effect by ear if we are at a sufficient distance from the sound source, no matter what — human conversation, bird singing or the sound made by a woodcutter in the forest. When making the above experiments, one condition is required to be fulfilled. An observer and a sound source should be located in a uniformly filled air environment; otherwise the process of changing the oscillations of sound waves will be distorted.

It was a whole different situation when it came to the application of the Doppler principle to optical phenomena. From the very beginning, Doppler himself believed that with the help of the principle he had discovered it was possible to determine radial velocities of the motion of celestial bodies. Doppler believed that the light spectrum from stars lies in the visible part and is a white spectrum, and the intensity of rays in ultraviolet

and infrared regions is insignificant. Having accepted this hypothesis, Doppler assumed that when a celestial body is in motion, part of the red or purple spectrum would disappear due to the fact that the entire spectrum shifted to a purple or red region, while the celestial body would acquire a red or purple hue. As a result, a star emitting the white light should appear to us as coloured red or purple. Based on that, Doppler admitted the possibility of determining the velocity of a celestial body relative to an observer on the Earth.

In his reasoning, Doppler did not pay attention to the Fraunhofer's earlier discovery about the presence of dark lines in the spectra of the Sun and other celestial bodies. In 1848, French physicist Armand Fizeau (1819–1896) pointed out the inaccuracy of Doppler's reasoning, noting that the dark lines in the spectra correspond to different wavelengths emitted by the source. Therefore, when a celestial body moves, the dark lines must shift in the spectrum observed by a stationary observer. Believing in the correctness of Doppler's ideas, Fizeau argued that by developing a method for measuring the displacement of these lines, it was possible to determine radial velocities of the motion of celestial bodies (see fig. 2). Subsequently, the method for determining radial velocity proposed by Fizeau was used in astronomy and is still used today.

Figure 2. Shift of dark lines in the wave spectrum

In 1852, Joseph Petzval, a famous Austrian physicist and mathematician, made objections to Doppler [2]. He denied the correctness of Doppler's conclusions and did not recognize the principle he had put forward. Petzval built his proof of the fallacy of the Doppler effect on the consideration of the case where the disturbance source and the receiver are stationary relative to each other while the entire medium is in motion. Having made calculations, he determined that the wave oscillation frequency coincided with the emitted one. Yet, according to Doppler's formulas, the oscillation frequency has the same result under the same conditions, too. Because of that, Petzval's proof was inconclusive. Later, a discussion arose between Petzval and Doppler. Petzval claimed that a physical law should be formulated as a purely objective law of nature and it should not include values that depend on the observer's perception or even on any observation means or the state of devices. According to Petzval, the law should have invariability in relation to any

observation means, including the devices used. Petzval also pointed out that the Doppler principle is premised on the subjective perceptions of observers, which does not give it the right to be called a physical law. Doppler, on the contrary, argued that values measured in the course of experiment should participate in the formulation of a physical law. In this regard, he referred to the authority of Newton and other scientists and philosophers — supporters of pure empiricism, and believed that Petzval reasoned in the spirit of the old scholastic philosophy.

The Doppler-Fizeau principle was not applied in science at first, but it was always in the scientists' field of view. In 1859, Gustav Kirchhoff and Robert Bunsen discovered spectrum analysis, showing that each element is characterized by its linear spectrum. In 1868, William Huggins discovered a shift of hydrogen lines in the spectrum of the Sirius star to the red end, in comparison with the hydrogen spectrum on the Earth. The Doppler effect was supported by Ernst Mach, an Austrian physicist and philosopher. Historically, everything turned in favour of accepting the Doppler effect as a law of nature. At present, we know that the dispute between Petzval and Doppler was resolved in favour of the latter. But who was really right? In order to find the truth for this question, we need to study the process of changing the wave frequency when the source and the receiver move relative to each other, not only by conducting empirical studies but also by involving a mathematical view of the processes taking place. It is only by using a multifaceted approach and applying an old and reliable logical thought that we will be able to get to the truth.

2. A Mathematical View of the Doppler-Fizeau Process

The adoption of the Doppler-Fizeau effect as a law of nature was of great importance for the subsequent development of such sciences as physics, astronomy and philosophy. After all, in fact, having made simple arithmetic transformations of the formula (1), we will derive a more familiar equation similar to the space transformation equations used:

$$\nu = \frac{1 \pm \frac{v_r}{v}}{1 \mp \frac{v_s}{v}} \nu_0 \quad (2)$$

Thus, having studied Doppler's work, Norwegian scientist Vogt set forth completely new mathematical ideas in 1887. Later, they turned out to be an expression of the main postulates of Albert Einstein's special theory of relativity. Vogt considered Doppler's formula (2) as mathematical transformations of x, y, z coordinates directly related to the medium, in which waves propagate to the coordinate system x', y', z' related to the motion of the source or the observer. In his work, Vogt showed for the first time that the Doppler principle could be considered not only as a result of spatial transformations of variables x, y, z . He introduced formulas for the transformation of coordinates and time, which allowed preserving invariability of the wave equation. After some time, based on Vogt's ideas, Lorentz developed formulas for space transformation, which later formed the basis of Einstein's theory of relativity. It should be noted that the transformation formulas of Vogt and Lorentz are mutually independent, as well as are invariable to the Doppler wave equations. As we can see from the above, the Doppler-Fizeau principle is not isolated from

the existing theories of science and has determined, up to date, the further development of philosophy, astronomy and physics. To understand the adoption of rather bold but insufficiently grounded decisions of the scientists of the 19th and early 20th centuries, we need to plunge into that time, at least a little. It should be noted that in the first half of the 19th century, the mathematical works by Nikolai Lobachevsky and János Bolyai were published. Their works destroyed the centuries-old foundations of philosophy and the structure of geometric space, laid down as far back as by Euclid. At first, the new geometry was not appreciated by Lobachevsky's contemporaries. Yet, with the appearance of a number of geometric space models in the second half of the 19th century, based on which non-Euclidean geometry was performed, more and more people of science gained faith in curvature and the possibility of existence of a multidimensional physical space.

Figure 3. Observer sees the railway in the distance

Simultaneously with the ongoing changes in mathematics and philosophy, physics received rapid development, too. In the 19th century, a variety of new laws were discovered in optics, thermodynamics, electricity and nuclear physics. Most of the natural phenomena discovered at that time had no logical or philosophical justification. Many scientists, trying to comprehend the state of physics, doubted the objective reality of science. Increasingly, they began to think that the laws of nature are not independent but depend on the consciousness of people. With the discovery of new phenomena in nature, the previously inherent logical sequence and the material basis of physics disappeared; scientists began to question the previously laid foundation of science. It is not nature that gives us laws, but we establish them and, in general, every law is nothing but the arrangement of our sensations, they thought.

A prominent representative of that era was the Austrian physicist and philosopher, Ernst Mach (1838-1916). He was a scientist who sought to comprehend and philosophically substantiate new discoveries in mathematics and physics, so abundant in his lifetime. The central core in physics and philosophy for Mach was the supremacy of experience. At the same time, he relied on direct sensory data and sensations. Mach promoted widely the principle of observation and rejected the old school of learning the truth based on

consistent logical thinking. Thus, in his arguments Ernst Mach rejected the theory of the atomic structure of matter predicted by ancient Greeks, based on his principle of the absence of observation. Later, Mach's philosophical views were criticized by many scientists of the 20th century and his philosophical teaching was recognized as erroneous. However, the paradox lies in the fact that, albeit the Doppler principle is recognized on the basis of Mach's rejected philosophy, it has remained a law of nature up to the present.

Based on the above, let us consistently get to the depths of what is happening in the Doppler process. Mach's ideas based on purely empirical views should in fact be questioned. In order not to be unfounded, let me give you a few examples. Based on visible sensations, people have been convinced for many millennia that the Sun and stars revolve around the Earth.

Figure 4. Ships at sea, on waves

Now we know that this is not true. Here are some more informative examples, which will question Mach's philosophy. In figure 3 above, we see a straight railway with an observer's look into the distance. We can see that two parallel rails converge in the distance; yet we know for sure that the actual distance between the rails remains unchanged. Let us consider another experimental study, the image of which is shown in fig. 4 below. We can see three ships that are located in different positions in relation to the waves at sea and are in motion. If we place observers on the upper decks of these three ships, the observer on the first ship atop will see that the waves do not change, regardless of the vessel speed. The second ship moves in the same direction with the waves and the observer sees waves with an increased length. The third ship is moving towards the waves; consequently, the observer will see waves with a shortened length relative to the sea waves. The reasoning of this kind is usually given in cases where they want to convince us of the truth of the Doppler effect as a law of nature. But if you think about it, the waves on the sea in fact remain unchanged, as well as the energy transmitted by them at the given part of the sea. What we really see is the illusion of the change in the wavelength, just as in the case where the observer in figure 3 is looking into the distance. Already at this stage, the processes taking place described as the Doppler effect, raise doubts as to their reality.

To get to the truth of the process taking place, we should not stop at this stage of cognition. After all, we really hear and see changes in the sound strength and brightness of the headlights of an approaching car. Also, we feel warm being near the campfire, and cold when being far from it. Then, what is really going on? To understand this, let us study the process in question by subjecting it to a mathematical research. Let us designate the source of energy radiation by O . Let us suppose that the energy source is

in a homogeneous medium, the radiation energy does not change per unit of time and is distributed evenly in all directions. For the ease of perception, figure 5 shows a sectional view of spheres in space with a plane passing through centre O . Therefore, we can see concentric circles in the figure. Figuratively, the spheres can be represented as a large onion with many concentric layers. Figure 5 shows energy source O , and all the energy produced from the source at the unit time at distance R is evenly distributed over the entire area of the sphere. As the distance to the source changes, the area of the sphere changes, while the amount of energy received by each surface of the sphere remains constant; only the density of the energy flow changes. We know that the area of sphere S is calculated by the formula:

$$S = 4\pi R^2,$$

where R – radius of the sphere. Consequently, the sphere surface area increases

Figure 5. Section of concentric spheres in space

when moving away from the source and decreases, accordingly, when approaching it. Since source energy E is a constant value, we can find energy density ρ_n on the sphere under study by a certain radius R_n :

$$\rho_n = \left(\frac{E}{4\pi R_n^2}\right). \quad (3)$$

From the derived formula (3) we can see that the change in energy density of the space surface under study is inversely proportional to the squared distance from energy source $1/R^2$.

By definition, from the textbook on physics for higher educational establishments, we find [3]: “The sound force, or intensity, in a transmitted (i.e. not standing) wave

is defined as the amount of energy transferred per second through a unit area of 1cm^2 perpendicular to the direction of wave propagation”. Based on this definition, already at this stage, we specifically know one of the possible reasons for the change in sound strength associated with the change in distance to the sound source. Yet, let us conduct additional research and find out under what other conditions the sound intensity will change. To do this, let us refer to the doctrine of waves and the causes that generate the sound process. We know that air is an elastic medium and sound waves are transmitted from the oscillation source by means of longitudinal oscillations of air molecules. Thus, the textbook on physics [3] reads as follows: “Longitudinal waves are an alternating series of compressions and rarefactions, while the wavelength, in the sense of this concept, is the distance between two adjacent compressions (fig. 6). Sound waves in liquids and gases are a typical example of longitudinal waves”.

Figure 6. Longitudinal waves in acoustics

Elasticity is the property of bodies to change shape and size under stress and to naturally recover the original configuration when external influences cease. The air has the properties of an elastic medium, and the interval between molecules under normal conditions is about 10^{-8} metres. In the presence of a source of external influences, there arises an oscillating system which sequentially transmits oscillations from adjacent particles to distant ones. In this oscillatory process, it is obvious that the medium molecules located at a distance from the place of initial disturbance will begin to oscillate only when an oscillatory process propagating sequentially, from one particle of the medium to another, has reached them over time. The molecules in Figure 6 above are displayed based on the experimental studies; we can see that in the process of transmitting disturbances, clumps of molecules are formed with sparse areas between them. Considering the wave process in more detail, it becomes clear that oscillations are made by a set of particles, and longitudinal waves are formed by transmitting energy from the source, gradually covering new areas of air. In order to simplify the process on the formation of longitudinal waves under study, let us conceptually imagine it as an oscillatory circuit where clumps of air molecules are represented as separate particles and arranged sequentially along the x axis from the oscillation source to the receiver (fig. 7 below). The sections with a rarefied air medium (fig. 6) can be neglected as they do not affect the overall oscillating system of particles. In the diagram shown (fig. 7), we can see that, provided that the source and the receiver are at rest, particle 1, having received an energy impulse from the source, oscillates to

particle 2 at speed v . Thus, sequentially from one particle to another, the oscillation is transmitted to particle n and to the sound receiver (the environmental resistance is not taken into account). Provided that the sound source moves towards the receiver, we will observe that particle 1 will move up to particle 2 at the speed of sound propagation in the air, let us assume $v = 1230\text{km}/h$. In fact, we know that the speed of ground vehicles is significantly lower than the sound speed. This means that further we will see that the sound source at speed v_s , which is less than speed v , will not reach particle 2. At the same time, according to the elasticity properties of the medium, particle 1 will perform the reverse motion and will not participate in the further oscillatory process, since the oscillation source has shifted forward. Having received energy from particle 1, particle 2 will transmit the oscillation to particle 3 and then will return to its original place, while the sound source will constantly lag behind and will

Figure 7. Diagram for sound wave energy transmission

have no effect on the oscillatory process. It follows that the sound source can affect the change in the sound strength in the only case — when its motion speed is a multiple of sound speed v equal to $1230\text{ km}/h$. Applying the velocity addition formula, let us find the sound speed v' received by the observer:

$$v' = v + v_s = n v, \quad (4)$$

where v – sound speed in the air; v_s – speed of the sound source. Since $v = v_s$, it is possible to introduce multiplicity factor n in whole numbers. Based on formula 4, we can explain many processes observed in nature. At the moment of transition from subsonic to supersonic speed, a stronger air wave emanates from a jet plane flying over the ground. Hence, we hear a sharp transition from a moderate sound to a strong one in the form of a sharp pop. The same effect, a sharp change in sound, my friends and I used to produce in childhood making a sharp crack with a whip, though it did not always work out. To make the process under study complete, let us consider the case where the sound source remains at place, and the observer moves towards the sound wave. In the diagram (fig. 7), we can see that when it moves to a particle $(n - 1)$ and $(n - 2)$, nothing changes in the diagram since the sound receiver cannot affect the air particles transmitting energy. However, the change in the sound strength registered by the observer will occur for another reason, namely in compliance with the law of dependence of the change in the received energy density on the squared distance to the oscillation source (3). The fulfillment of this law in

an air environment is easily explained — after all, the energy from the oscillation source is transmitted not only to clumps of molecules along the x axis, but also to particles in the entire volume space around the axis. It is specifically due to the change in distance that energy is redistributed along the wave front surface and we hear a change in the sound strength. The option from the Doppler process where the source and the receiver are moving in opposite directions should not be considered, since these shifts will not affect the change in sound intensity; you can verify this by yourself conducting similar mental studies.

From the history of learning the Doppler-Fizeau effect, we know that the Doppler principle in optics was adopted on the basis of experiments with sound. But now we have definitely proved that the Doppler formulas in acoustics are wrong, since the change in sound strength occurs for completely different reasons. We could stop here and recognize the Doppler-Fizeau effect as erroneous in optics too, as it does not work in acoustics. Yet, this decision would be hasty, after all we do not know the actual circumstances of what is happening, namely the reasons for changing the parameters of optical waves. From experience, we know that optical waves have a big difference compared to sound. First of all, optical waves are not longitudinal but transverse. Secondly, they have a dual nature, since they simultaneously have the properties of a wave and a particle (corpuscle). Let us also note that optical waves are formed in atoms and have the essence of electromagnetic radiation in the form of individual energy quantum called photons that can move in a vacuum. Studying the spectra to distant stars and galaxies, a lot of astronomers noticed the typical properties of the spectrum, namely, depending on the distance to the object under study, there was observed a shift of the Fraunhofer lines z depending on the wavelength:

$$z = \frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0}, \quad (5)$$

where λ_0 – radiated wavelength, λ – observed wavelength. A lot of astronomers found an explanation for this phenomenon of nature based on its connection with the Doppler effect.

In 1929, American astronomer Edwin Hubble reported he had discovered the fundamental regularity. He found that the dark lines in the spectrum of all galaxies, with the exception of a few galaxies from among the closest ones, are shifted towards the red end. Hubble explained this phenomenon, as usual, by the Doppler effect. Based on this, he concluded that all galaxies, with the exception of a few, are moving away from us, and the recession velocity v of each galaxy is determined from the proportion as follows [4]:

$$\frac{v}{c} = \frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} = z, \quad (6)$$

where c – speed of light. Exploring the issue in question in more detail, Hubble established that the redshift z in the spectra is proportional to the distance to the galaxies [4]:

$$c \frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} = cz = Hr, \quad (7)$$

where c – speed of light; H – proportionality coefficient for determining distance r to distant stars and galaxies. The discovered regularity acquired the character of a universal

law. This law, called the redshift in spectra of galaxies, is a fundamental law in astronomy, sometimes called Hubble's law. But is it possible to state that the redshift in the spectra of galaxies is a consequence of the Doppler effect, i.e. that it is caused by the recession of galaxies? If we assume that this is the case, then it follows from formulas [4] (6) and (7) that

$$v = Hr. \quad (8)$$

Based on this formula, scientists adopted the concept of galaxy recession, hence the Big Bang theory. Hubble's assumption described by formula (8) is still used in astronomical research. Thus, it was recognized in 1998 that the Universe is expanding, even with acceleration. And since this contradicts the existing laws of nature, a new concept was introduced in physics — dark energy. However, it should be understood that the law (7) is correct, it has been verified by long-term observations. And the law (8) is only true under the assumption that the spectral shift is caused by the Doppler effect.

It should be noted that at present, astronomers do not use the formula (6) to calculate the speed of faintly visible distant galaxies. However, to confirm the existing theories of the structure of the outer space, they use a formula based on the assumption of the correctness of the Doppler Effect and A. Einstein's theory of relativity, which has the following from [4]:

$$\frac{v}{c} = \frac{(z+1)^2-1}{(z+1)^2+1}. \quad (9)$$

The equation (9) can help to easily determine the speed of galaxies v . It is not difficult to note that no matter how large the shifts of the spectra we observe, according to this formula, the speed of recession will be less than the speed of light c .

From the formula (5), we can see that as the wavelength increases, the spectral shift z increases, too. Then, what is really going on? For a detailed study of electromagnetic radiation, let us return to the universal law of nature (3), described above. Let us assume that there is a distant star or galaxy in the centre O (Fig. 5); let us also note that the initial energy from the source does not disappear anywhere and the energy conservation law is observed. The energy emitted by the star does not disappear with the increased distance R , and all of it is evenly distributed over the area of the sphere with radius R_n . The observer's small telescope located on the radius sphere R_n captures only optical waves called a luminous flux. According to the source [4]: *"The luminous flux I of the star is the amount of energy radiated by the star incident per unit time on a surface unit, perpendicular to the line of sight"*. That is, the density of radiated energy or the number of photons per unit time per unit area changes inversely proportional to the squared distance from the reference energy measurement $1/R^2$. Thus, we have determined that as the distance from the star to the observer increases, the amount of energy coming to the telescope mirror decreases. In addition to the above energy change associated with decreased count of photons entering the telescope receiver, astronomers have found that with increasing distance to the source of electromagnetic waves, the wavelength of each recording quantum increases. Using the classical formula for determining the energy of one quantum:

$$E = \frac{hc}{\lambda}, \quad (10)$$

where h – Planck’s constant, c – is the speed of light, λ – is the wavelength, as well as considering that there are two constant values in the numerator of formula (10), we find that as the wavelength increase, the energy of the received quantum also decreases. On the basis of the above facts resulting from the formulas (3) and (10) and confirmed by many years of research by scientists, we observe that the radial velocity of the source and the observer does not participate in any way in the processes of the observed change in the electromagnetic wave parameters. Therefore, the radial velocity of the oscillation source and the observer simply cannot influence the shift of dark lines in the spectra of the studied waves.

All the time, throughout the text above, we have considered the cases of the formation of electromagnetic waves where the source and the observer were on the same axis and were moving with radial velocities relative to each other. Let us consider a very unusual case of motion, in my opinion, where there is also a shift of dark lines in the wave spectrum. In 1871, German astronomer Hermann Karl Vogel (1841-1907), in an attempt to confirm the validity of the Doppler principle, conducted the following experiment. In his research, he used a special spectroscope invented by Zollner, with the help of which Vogel could observe the spectra of two opposite edges near the solar disk equator side by side. As a result of the observation, the dark lines of these two spectra turned out to be shifted relative to each other. In the future, these experiments were carried out by many scientists not only in the Sun, but also in the conditions of the Earth. Conducting experiments with rotating bodies in the laboratory turned out to be difficult due to low speeds. To get out of this situation, scientists invented special devices, the construction of which was based on either of two ways – to obtain a greater radial velocity, or to significantly increase the dispersion of spectral devices. The first method was used by Russian astronomer Aristarkh Belopolsky in Pulkovo [5] and [6]. The second method was used by French scientists Fabry and Perot in Marseille [5]. Using the invented device, Belopolsky observed a change in the light wavelength at a radial velocity from $0,25km/s$ to $0,67km/s$, while the measurement error was about 5%. Fabry and Perot conducted more accurate studies using their device; the measurement error was no more than 2%. They observed the change in the light wavelength at the radial velocity of the rotating disk equal to $0,1km/s$. After conducting the experiments, the scientists found the reason for the change in the wavelength in the Doppler effect. They proceeded from the fact that in the experiments with sound waves conducted earlier, the correctness of the Doppler effect was confirmed. And based on this and Fizeau’s assumption that the radial velocity of the source or the observer is the cause of the change in the optical wavelength, they came to the conclusion that the Doppler-Fizeau principle was true. In order to understand what is really happening when the wave radiation generator rotates around its axis, let us conduct our own investigation. To do this, let us schematically show the observation plane of the solar equator from the Earth (Fig. 8). Figure 8 (top and bottom images) shows the Sun S , on the left, and an observer on the Earth at point E , on the right. Let us assume that the Sun does not rotate around its axis (fig. 8, top image) nor does it move along the SE line, and

that it radiates the same amount of energy in all directions. Under such conditions, an observer on the Earth will not see changes in the wave spectrum at diagonally located points A and B . The number of photons will change only when we assume that the Sun is moving towards the Earth. Consequently, based on the fulfillment of equality (3) the energy received by the observer will change according to the inversely proportional squared change in distance between the source and the receiver, while the observer will register an increased luminous flux from the star. At the same time, it should be noted that when simultaneously observing points A and B , the spectral lines of both spectra will coincide.

Figure 8. Observation plane of the solar equator from Earth, top view

Figure 8 (bottom image) shows real conditions — the Sun rotates at angular velocity ω to the left, and the distance to the receiver on the Earth during the observation is conditionally constant. At present, it is known that a quantum particle is characterized by the wave-particle duality, that is, a photon has the properties of both a particle and a wave. We also know that modern science does not know the structure or size of light quantum. Yet, let us assume that the photon carries some specific energy. The frequencies of light radiation are in the range of $\nu = 3,9 \cdot 10^{-14} \dots 7,9 \cdot 10^{-14}$. Let us take an average value for the study equal to $\nu = 6 \cdot 10^{-14}$. Let us assume that one photon carries the energy contained in one oscillation period, i.e. one Sun atom emits $6 \cdot 10^{14}$ quanta of light per second. We also know that the linear velocity at the Sun equator is equal to $v \approx 2 \text{ km/s}$. Based on these data, let us determine the linear distance L which the atom will pass for time T before the next photon emission:

$$L = vT = 2(6 \cdot 10^{-14}) = 12 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ km} = 1,2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}.$$

The size of one hydrogen atom in diameter equals to $12 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}$. Based on this, it is not

difficult to calculate that during the Sun rotation around the axis, the number of atoms involved in the emission of photons will change every 10 radiations of the observed atom. Let the atom under study be located at point A (fig. 8, bottom image); in $T = 6 \cdot 10^{-13}$ seconds it will be located at point A' , and in its place there will be a completely new atom that will also begin to emit photons. Taking into account only one atom at point A , the Sun will emit by $6 \cdot 10^{13}$ more photons per each second of exposure in the direction of the observer, due to the rotation process. Accordingly, at point B , the observer will see by $6 \cdot 10^{13}$ fewer photons per one second, due to the rotation process. We have determined the time period for the changes in the amount of the registered energy, when the atoms are arranged in a row and emit quanta simultaneously. However, it should be taken into account that the observer during the exposure observes the radiation emanating from a certain surface of the Sun. Therefore, it is safe to say that a very large number of atoms are involved in the radiation of energy (one gram of hydrogen contains $3 \cdot 10^{23}$ atoms) and they all emit portions of energy at different times. From the experiments conducted in the conditions of the Earth, we know that the energy flow caused by the rotation of the body is already registered by devices at the rotation speed of $0,1 km/s$. This means that the effect of the Sun rotation involves not only newly appearing atoms, but also atoms that were visible initially.

From the experiments carried out in laboratories and based on observations of the Sun, we find that when the source rotates, the energy flow changes. The concomitant cause of the change in the registered energy is the change in the distance at some period of time dt . Given that the frequency of photon emission is about (10^{14}) per second, then at a speed of $v = 0,1 km/s$, the observed point will move to the distance ds and this is enough for our devices to detect the change in the energy flow. We have inexorably come to observe the rule of energy change, which is directly dependent on the distance between the source and the observer. Based on the fact that light waves make $6 \cdot 10^{14}$ oscillations per second, the speed of $v = 0,1 km/s$ is enough for a chain of changes to occur. When the distance changes by value ds , the number of photons registered by the observer as a new wavelength changes too. Although observations of the Sun and experiments conducted in the conditions of the Earth are not the same in the origin of the energy received by the receiver, I would generally call this process the effect of a rotating body. In the conditions of the Earth, we face a lot of examples where similar processes occur due to the rotation of the body. Thus, rotating in a homogeneous medium, an airplane propeller and a marine vessel propeller, on the one hand, have a medium compression; on the other hand, a rarefaction. And if we imagine the air and water environment as energy, then we observe a change in energy due to the effect of a rotating body at a certain minimum speed. These reflections are simple but they are very important for a complete understanding of the processes taking place. Nature itself laid down the properties of electromagnetic waves during their formation; after all, the optical wave is not integral as it visually seems to us, but is composed of individual quanta of energy. When studying celestial bodies that are close enough to the Earth, when analyzing the spectral line shift, we should take into account the changes in distance — both the radial displacement relative to each other and

the change in distance associated with the effect of energy source rotation. Thus, analyzing the conducted research, we can say with confidence that motion speed of the source or the observer as well as the linear distance between them, are only accompanying parameters for changing the radiation energy. Therefore, the law of velocity addition is inapplicable for light quanta; and it is only for this reason that the speed of light is a constant value in nature. We can achieve the opposite only by changing the nature of the electromagnetic wave, by making the wave continuous. Only then, the law of velocity addition will be fulfilled and the speed of light will change its value. Yet, even admitting this imaginary assumption, it should be noted that even in this case, the observer's motion speed will not affect the speed of the optical wave in any way. This is because the receiver's motion cannot and does not affect the formation of an optical wave coming from the oscillation source.

3. Conclusion

Describing many processes in this article, I have tried to explain the phenomena occurring in nature in an intelligible form. However, this is not always possible since one person can get the moment of clarity immediately while another needs simpler examples to understand the essence of the law of nature. Yet, still, let us analyze the information set forth in the article. In addition to determining the errors in the Doppler-Fizeau effect, I would like to highlight the equality (3) on determining the energy density, according to the law of inverse proportionality of the squared distance to the initial energy source. In applying it to space, we can see that a distant star or galaxy cannot be visible at an infinite distance. This is because the energy emitted by a star is a finite value, and the distance to the energy source can be infinitely large. Just at one fine moment, an observer on the Earth will see one random photon from a distant energy source through a telescope. That is why the stars in the sky do not fully illuminate the Earth's firmament. It also follows from the law (3) that the energy flow decreases as the distance increases. Then, on the basis of formulas characterizing electromagnetic waves $E = h\nu$ and $c = \nu\lambda$, and taking into account the invariability of light speed c , we find that the wavelength increases with distance, while the oscillation frequency decreases. We also know that as the distance to the stars increases, there is an increase in the displacement of spectrum lines. From all of this, and according to logic, it follows that an electromagnetic wave loses its energy with distance and turns into a microwave spectrum region instead of an optical wave. Thus, when modern science was able to record the radiation of the microwave background at a distance of 46.5 billion light years, it was not actually the relic radiation from the Big Bang theory but the view of distant galaxies in space. It was the limit of our view into the space distance that the Planck satellite of the European Space Agency detected with its sensitive devices (fig. 9). Based on the results of the research conducted in the article, we have come to the conclusion that the redshift z , and in general the Doppler effect, cannot be used for determining the radial velocity to distant stars and galaxies. Yet, this is easily fixable — after all, modern telescopes are equipped with charge-coupled devices. The CCD matrix has the property of getting a charge due to the

photoelectric effect. That is, energy can accumulate and images can be created with the help of electrons. Based on the features of this device, we can determine the amount of energy received during the exposure. As a rule, astronomers observe the flashes of distant type 1a supernovae at the moment of their stable glow. By measuring the amount of energy received during the same exposure time for several days and knowing the speed of electromagnetic waves, we can determine whether a given galaxy is moving or at rest, and develop in future a method for finding radial velocities of stars and galaxies. People of science who work directly with this equipment should implement this technique in life.

Figure 9. Limit of our view into space distance

Nowadays, when scientists discover unknown natural phenomena that do not correspond to the existing theory, they introduce new quantities and definitions. This reminds me of the science of ancient times, when the center of the world was the Earth and scientists explained the location of the stars and the movement of the planets and the Sun around the Earth using Aristotle's celestial spheres and Ptolemy's epicycles. After the adoption of new laws in science, describing the processes occurring in nature, all errors and the laws describing them will disappear like last year's snow.

I would like to clarify the results of the study conducted in article 1. The main point is to reveal the existing misunderstanding of the true processes involved in the Doppler effect. It is established that the described formula for the Doppler effect is erroneous for sound and optical waves and, as a consequence, will also be erroneous for the whole relativistic Einstein theory. Since the Doppler effect is not a law of nature, A. Einstein's work on special and general relativity is erroneous, since it uses the same concept of changing parameters described by the Doppler effect, only in an expanded application. Therefore, the application of this theory to explain processes in atomic physics, near and deep space, as well as in the theory of the origin of the Universe is unacceptable. It is difficult, but we have to admit that the measurements previously carried out by astronomers to determine the motion of distant stars and galaxies are incorrect; there is neither dark energy nor dark matter in space. The sooner we realize the above mistakes, the sooner we will understand the nature of the Universe. At the very beginning of the article the question is raised, "Is the Doppler effect a law of nature?". According to the results of the study, we unequivocally say that it is not a law of nature. It turns out

that the well-known formula describes only our vision of the phenomena of nature. In the text of the article a detailed analysis is carried out, as a result we have a general, correct description not of the phenomena, but of the processes occurring in nature. And I consider it my duty to bring this truth to the scientific society. The material described herein takes only one step towards unravelling the mystery of the creation of the All. In the following articles, we'll learn much new and interesting. With each step toward unraveling the mysteries of the Universe, we'll become convinced of the validity of the misconceptions already described, as well as many others yet unmentioned, and marvel at the beauty of the laws of nature. Are we ready to go further?

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